
DETERMINATION OF HEAVY METAL CONTENT OF SELECTED PACKAGED SPICES SOLD IN OWERRI METROPOLIS

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Abstract

Spices are used all over the world for culinary purposes. They are valued for their distinctive flavours, colors and aromas, although they contain some undesirable components that can be harmful like heavy metals, pesticides etc. The persistence and bioaccumulation potentials of these toxicants have significant impacts on human health. This study was aimed to determine the levels of heavy metals in ten packaged natural spices that are most popular in Owerri Metropolis, Imo State, Nigeria. The heavy metal contents were determined by Flame atomic absorption spectrometry. Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr) and Nickel (Ni) were assessed and compared with FAO/WHO, EU Standards. The ranges of concentrations of the heavy metals were: Lead 0.001-15.91kg, Cadmium 0.001 mg/kg, Chromium 1.27-6.96 mg/kg, Nickel 2.76-14.83 mg/kg respectively. Most of the levels of concentrations of heavy metals in the spices were within the safe limits with the exception of Chromium which was above the standard safe limits as approved by FAO/WHO in all the samples assessed. Consumers of these spices would not be exposed to any risk associated with the daily intake of 10g of spices per day as far as metals (Lead, Cadmium and Nickel) were concerned.

Keywords: Spices, Toxicants, Contamination, Heavy metals, Owerri Metropolis, Imo State.

1. Introduction

Spices are defined by Geneva International Organization for Standards as vegetable products or mixtures therefore free from extraneous matter, used for flavoring, seasoning and imparting aroma to foods(Jessica *et al.*,2015).Spices have been used since ancient civilization. Their piquancy and therapeutic potentials make them important for culinary and medicinal uses (Parthasarathy *et al.*, 2008). Many spices have been documented to possess anti- diabetic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-hypertensive potential (Srinivasan, 2005). A spice may be available in several forms: fresh, whole, dried, or pre-ground dried. Generally, spices are dried (Trainter, 2001).

Even though spices have many benefits, they can also contain some toxic chemicals derived from the environment of their production, processing and storage conditions. During harvesting, sun drying, processing and storage, spices can be contaminated. Also, open air drying leads to contamination of spices with soil and dust (Peter, 2006).

Heavy metals are any metallic element that has a proportionally high density and is poisonous at low concentrations. They are non-biodegradable in natural environment (Ab del-Rahman, 2022). Heavy metals can accumulate and contaminate spices through various means such as atmospheric decomposition by road sides, the soil type where the spice is grown on, polluted water source for their production and washing when displayed in the market (Aboyeji *et al.*, 2016). Heavy metals such as lead (Pb), Chromium (Cr), titanium (Ti) and copper (Cu) may migrate through industrial equipment, packaging materials and the environment processing methods and through food handlers who do not observe food hygiene regulations (Bradley *et al.*, 2005). Heavy metal contamination of food items is observed to be one of the most important aspects of food quality assurance (Khan *et al.*, 2009).

National Food Laws aims to protect citizens from health hazards. These laws and regulations include the quality of herbs and spices people consume and the specified maximum permissible limits of possible contaminants (Peter, 2006). Consumers are increasingly aware of their health and are looking for more comprehensive information on the safety of the food they consume. Thus, screening of packaged spices for heavy metals concentrations will make consumers to be conscious of the levels of these contaminants and be found in food seasonings and spices and this will in turn enable them to be aware of the toxicants levels when purchasing these foods.

2. Materials and Methods

Description of Study Area

Different retail outlets/ Supermarkets located in Owerri Metropolis (Egbu, Amakohia, Douglas and Irete) in Imo State, Nigeria.

Sample Collection/preparation

Ten natural packaged spices (Basil leaf, Bay leaves, Thyme, Sage, Parsley, Coriander, Oregano leaves, Rosemary, Marjoram and Mint) were randomly purchased in triplicate from retail outlets/Supermarkets to minimize experimental errors in analysis. The packaged spices were brands of three different manufacturers. Each sample was assigned an identity code and sent to the laboratory for analysis.

Table 1: Common and Scientific Names of Studied Spices

Common name	Scientific name
Basil leaves	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>
Bay leaves	<i>Laurus nobilis</i>
Thyme	<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>
Sage	<i>Salvia officinalis</i>
Parsley	<i>Petroselinum crispum</i>
Coriander	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>
Oregano leaves	<i>Origanum vulgare L.</i>
Rosemary	<i>Rosamarinus officinalis</i>
Marjoram	<i>Origanum majorana</i>
Mint	<i>Mentha rotundifolia</i>

Heavy Metal Analysis

For Determination of heavy metal concentration, a wet digestion of the dried spice samples was done according to the method described by Al-Eed *et al.*, 2002 using Conc. H₂SO₄ and 30% H₂O₂ mixture. To a 0.5g of dry- ground sample placed in 100ml beaker was added 3.5ml of 30% H₂O₂. The content of the beaker was heated to 100°C and the temperature was gradually increased to 250°C and left at this temperature for 30 minutes. The beaker was cooled and more 1ml of 30% H₂O₂ was added to the digestion mixture and the contents were reheated again. The digestion process was repeated more than one time until clear solution was obtained. The clear solution was obtained. The clear solution was transferred into 50ml volumetric flask, and completed to the mark with double distilled deionized water. A blank digestion solution was made for comparison. A standard solution for each element under investigation was prepared and used for calibration. Metal measurement was performed with a Perkin-Elmer model 2380 Atomic Absorption Spectrometer, double beam and deuterium background correction. Hollow cathode lamps of lead(Pb), Cadmium(Cd), Chromium(Cr) and Nickel(Ni) were used at specific wave length of metals as follows Pb(217nm), Cd(228.8nm), Cr(357.3nm), Ni(232.0nm). Measurements were done against metal standard solutions.

$$\text{Concentration (mg/kg)} = \frac{\text{Concentration of metal (mg/1) } \times \text{Volume of digest(l)}}{\text{Weight of sample (kg)}}$$

Statistical Data Analysis

Means and standard deviations were computed using Statistic Centurion XV, 2005 Version 15 Statistical software (Statpointinc., USA). One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to separate the means and significant differences compared using least significant difference (LSD) at $p < 0.05$ between concentrations of heavy metals in spices using the same software.

3. Results and Discussions

The concentrations of lead, Cadmium, Chromium and Nickel in the studied spice samples were presented in Table 2. The values of heavy metal concentration were compared with the maximum permissible concentration of 100, 0.2, 0.5, and 50 mg/kg for Pb, Cd, Cr and Ni respectively as recommended by (FAO/WHO 1984).

The lead concentrations of different samples are given in Table 2. Basil leaves had the highest concentration of 15.91 mg/kg while bay leaves had the least concentration of 0.001 mg/ kg. The high concentration of lead in basil leaves could be attributed to several factors such as high traffic density of the places they may have been dried. Piron- Frenet *et al.*, (1994) reported that lead levels in vegetation increased linearly with traffic density. Concentration of heavy metals in bay leaves (0.001 mg/kg) affirmed the report of Divrikli *et al.*, (2006) and Nnorom *et al.*, (2007) which showed that lead concentration could be insignificant or non- detectable in some spices and herbs. Rosemary had a lead for concentration of 3.66 mg/kg. This value is lower than the report of Marian and Cosmos (2010) which recorded 99 mg/ kg in Rosemary spice. Also Marian and Cosmos (2010) reported that lead exposure has been shown to cause severe anemia, permanent brain damage etc. However, the results of this study showed that the levels of lead in all the spice samples were below the FAO/WHO (1984) limit of 100 mg/ kg. The acceptable lead concentration limit for adults is 0.21 mg/ day (FAO/WHO, 1993).

As shown in Table 2, the concentrations of Cadmium in all the spice samples under investigation were 0.001 mg/kg. Comparing the Cadmium levels with the safety limits, it was found to be below the limit of 0.2 mg/ kg as given by (FAO/WHO, 2001). Cabrera *et al.*, 1995 reported that Cadmium content in food seasonings could be due to Contamination of raw materials, technological processes or colouring agents used as they contain cadmium salts. Ziyaina et al., 2014 reported that cadmium concentration in mixed spices was 0.36 mg/kg which was higher than the value recorded in this study. Cadmium toxicity is characterised by chest pain, cough with foamy and bloody sputum (Duruibe *et al.*, 2007). Cadmium is classified as human carcinogen (Waalkes, 2003), therefore increasing level of this toxic element in food is harmful. The acceptable daily intake of Cadmium is 0.006-0.007 mg/ day (FAO/WHO, 1993).

Table 2: Mean Concentration of the Heavy Metals in Selected Spice Samples

PARAMETERS (mg/kg)	LAA	LBA	SAMPLES LCA	LDA	LEA	LSD	FAO/WHO LIMITS (mg/kg)
Lead	15.91 ^a ±0.01	0.001 ⁱ ± 0.006	5.13 ^g ±0.02	11.06 ^b ±0.05	6.84 ^e ±0.05	0.06	100
Cadmium	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	-	0.2
Chromium	1.86 ^d ±0.02	1.71 ^e ±0.09	2.74 ^b ±0.04	6.96 ^a ±0.01	1.28 ^g ±0.06	0.11	0.5
Nickel	6.04 ^d ±0.04	14.83 ^a ±0.02	4.84 ^f ±0.06	11.84 ^b ±0.01	12.06 ^b ±0.05	0.34	50

Results are mean ± standard deviation of 3 determinations, mean values followed by different superscripts within a column are significant (p< 0.05)

KEY:

LAA = Basil leaves (*Ocimum gratissimum*)

LBA = Bay leaves (*Larus nobilis*)

LCA = Thyme leaves (*Thymus vulgaris*)

LDA = Sage (*Salvia officinalis L.*)

LEA = Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*)

Continuation of table 2 : Mean Concentration of the Heavy Metals in Selected Spice Samples

PARAMETERS (mg/kg)	SAMPLES					LSD	FAO/WHO LIMITS (mg/kg)
	LFA	LGA	LHA	LIA	LJA		
Lead	6.90 ^d ±0.05	5.24 ^f ±0.06	3.66 ^h ±0.01	9.15 ^c ±0.03	6.80 ^e ±0.03	0.06	100
Cadmium	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	0.001±0.00	-	0.2
Chromium	1.53 ^f ±0.01	1.43 ^f ±0.03	1.27 ^g ±0.03	2.42 ^c ±0.02	1.65 ^e ±0.06	0.11	0.5
Nickel	2.76 ^h ±0.03	5.00 ^f ±0.01	3.13 ^g ±0.02	9.39 ^c ±0.06	5.38 ^e ±0.02	0.34	50

Results are mean ± standard deviation of 3 determinations, mean values followed by different superscripts within a column are significant (p< 0.05)

KEY:

LFA = Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*)

LGA = Oregano leaves (*Origanum vulgare L.*)

LHA = Rosemary (*Rosamarinus officinals*)

LIA = Marjoram (*Origanum majorana*)

LJA = Mint (*Mentha rotundifolia*)

The investigation showed that the concentrations of chromium ranged from 1.27-6.96 mg/ kg. Sage spice had the highest concentration of chromium with a value of 6.96 mg/kg while rosemary had the least concentration (1.27 mg/kg). The maximum permitted concentration of chromium in food is 1 mg/kg as recommended by International/National standards for heavy metals in food (Bakhru, 2003). However, going by this standard; the values obtained in this study were higher. Divrikli *et al.* (2006) reported the range of chromium to be 0.1- 9.7 ug/g in eleven different spices and herbal plant species. Another study by Hifsa *et al.* (2009) reported that chromium level was within the range of 115-368 mg/ kg in spice samples. These values were quite higher when compared to those obtained in this investigation. The recommended dietary intake for chromium is 0.035 mg/day for male and 0.0025 mg/day for females (Food and Nutrition Board, 2001). Chromium can be present in the diet mainly as Cr (III) (Codex, 1995). Cr (III) has a low toxicity due to low absorption (about 0.5%) (Nordic Council of Ministers, 1995).

Nickel concentrations ranged from 2.76- 14.83 mg/ kg. Concentration of Nickel was exceptionally high in bay leaves (14.83 mg/kg) compared to other spice samples studied. Nickel is found in small quantities in many foodstuffs (0.001-0.01 mg/kg) but in higher quantities in foodstuffs such as grains, nuts, cocoa products and seeds (up to 0.8 mg/ kg) (National Food Agency of Denmark, 1995). Denise *et al.* (2021) reported that the concentrations of nickel varied from 0.376-0.8 mg/ kg for mint, 0.354_0.427 mg/ kg for rosemary. These values were low compared to those obtained in this study. Nickel is found as complex bound Ni ²⁺ ions (Codex, 1995). The absorption of free nickel ions released in the gastrointestinal tract may be 40 times higher than that of complex- bound nickel from food materials (Sunderman *et al.*, 1989).

4. Conclusion

This study showed that heavy metals were present at different concentrations, which in few cases exceeded the permissible limits. The levels of lead, chromium and nickel were found in appreciable amounts, unlike Cadmium that was insignificant and below permissible limits. The highest content of lead and chromium were recorded in bay leaves and Sage. However, considering the small quantities in which spices are used generally, these samples may not constitute health hazards but continuous usage overtime can be a threat to health.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing of interest.

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